

Users' Perceived Value on E-Banking Services - An Empirical Study

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Abstract

The world has come to a point where computers and the internet has been a necessity rather than a luxury, E-Commerce which stands for electronic commerce is an activity which is adopted to use electronically inclined system or an infrastructure in conducting business. Services or goods are traded using this as a medium for business to business, business to customer and customer to customer.

The essence of this research article is to explore the users' perceived value on e-banking services offered by commercial banks in Bangalore and to throw a light on the core facts that are closely associated with e-banking. It will also interpret on how customers are responding to the changes from traditional banking system to the new system and how comfortable they are when it comes to using the modern methods.

Introduction

The evolution of e-banking has gained an impetus in this modern era of economy. Commercial banks have traditionally been in the forefront of harnessing technology to improve their products, services and efficiency. They have been, over a long period of time, using the electronic and the telecommunication networks for the delivery of wide range of value added products and services. The delivery channels include direct dial – up connections, private networks, public networks, etc and the devices include telephone, Personal Computers (PCs) including the Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), etc.

With the high popularity of PC's, there is easy access to Internet and World Wide Web (WWW). Internet has been increasingly used by the banks as a medium for receiving instructions and also for delivering their products and services to their customers. This form of banking is generally referred to as digital banking, although the range of products and services offered by different banks vary widely both in their content and sophistication. Digital banking, both as a medium of delivery of banking services and as a strategic tool

for business development, have gained wider acceptance internationally and is fast catching up in India with more and more banks entering the fray.

Thus, the degree of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty to a specific bank has been a major concern for many banks. In the past, clients used to face long queues when they go to banks, where they had to spend too much of their working time waiting for their turn. Often, banks are not open in the afternoons or in vacations.

Some scholars have shown that many international internet users demonstrate similar behaviors and preferences across nations for example. Some studies have examined the issues on the evolution of digital banking in Malaysia and investigated the success factors in various-delivery channels in the Malaysian banking scenario. Some have investigated customer preferences of digital banking in Malaysia.

This study examines the users' perceived view on digital banking services and to explore the significant aspects that are oriented with digital banking in Bangalore. Also, this paper assesses whether the perceived value of digital banking services in Bangalore was constrained by the technology, particularly on the basis of different demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation, monthly income level, computer literacy, smart phone availability, and internet accessibility at home/office. Findings of this study are useful for the banking sector in formulating appropriate strategies to meet or exceed customer satisfaction, build customer loyalty and retain the potential customers.

Review of Literature

- The prior research on e-banking services has empirically found positive relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness as critical factors on the use of digital banking. Digital banking provides higher degree of convenience that enables customers to access internet banking at all times and places. Apart from that, the accessibility of computers has been perceived as a measure of the relative advantage. Therefore, it is hypothesized that convenience and accessibility have positive effect on consumer adoption of digital banking.
- In the present context of the market scenario determining awareness and adoption of technology based banking services among rural customers and demographic factors like age, education level, profession and income influences the awareness level is highly important.
- Obviously, the customers have many doubts about the trust ability of the E-Bank's privacy policies. The trust has a striking influence on the user's willingness to engage in the online exchanges of money and the personal sensitive information. Perceived usefulness is defined as the extent to which a person believes that using a system enhances job performance, while perceived ease of use is defined as a person believes that using a system will be free of effort.

The present study focuses on exploring the users' perceived view on digital banking service offered by banks in Bangalore. According to various academics (Cheng et al., 2006, the following factors were observed to be the key factors to perform incredibly in exploring user views, a concept that appears to be extremely significant in the context of the present study. The proposed conceptual framework examines the causal relationship between research constructs: (i) Perceived usefulness, (ii) Perceived ease of use, (iii) Perceived enjoyment, (iv) Quality of internet connection, and (v) Perceived risk.

Objective of the Study

The core objective of this study is to explore the users perceived value on the prominent dimensions that are closely associated with digital banking services rendered by commercial banks in Bangalore.

- To understand the convenience of the customers with respect to E banking.
- To identify whether the customers are aware of E banking services.

Methodology

The core theme of this study is to explore the users' perceived value on the prominent dimensions that are closely associated with E-banking services rendered by commercial banks in Bangalore. In order to realize this OBJECTIVE of the study, the following two hypotheses were effectively framed by the researchers.

- **H1:** The users, who are inclined to use the modern technology, are likely to access the E-banking services provided by commercial banks in Bangalore.
- **H2:** Test for a significant difference in the users' perceived value on various facets of E-banking services on the basis of their demographic characteristics.

From the relevant literatures and factor analysis of this study, seven critical dimensions of E-banking services were identified, namely (i) ease of use, (ii) convenience, (iii) trust & reliability, (iv) Cost effective, (v) time savings, (vi) privacy & security. Anonymous & structured questionnaires with five-point Likert scale were administered to a total number of 80 respondents sampled from major areas of Bangalore on the basis of area-cum-purposeful sampling technique.

To assure the convenience and avoid the bias, the questionnaires were effectively administered to the users who were highly exposed to various E-banking services rendered by commercial banks in Bangalore. The questionnaires were circulated to the respondents through online and also few were distributed face-to-face and the response rate was quite satisfactory. To ensure content validity, the items used in the questionnaire were constructed on the basis of the extensive literatures as discussed above. To assure their views properly on the subject, the screening questions were asked to ensure that the respondents have been accessed digital or virtual or electronic banking services before.

However, and wherever possible, the researchers used validated measures that have been previously applied. The reliability and validity of the constructs and scale items used in the research instrument were tested through pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha. Two consecutive rounds of pre-testing were conducted in order to ensure that the respondents could understand the measurement scales used in this study. First, the questionnaire was reviewed by the academic researchers experienced in questionnaire design and development and next, the questionnaire was piloted with the experts in the domain of digital banking services. Pre-test of the questionnaire was conducted to a small sample of 20 bankers who are accessing to and users of the digital banking services. Respondents were asked to indicate their levels of agreement based on the five-point Likert scale from "1" (strongly disagree) to "5" (strongly agree).

Findings of the Study. The major findings of this study can include demographics of the sample, descriptive statistics of the research variables, and outcomes of one-way ANOVA results of the research variables.

Demographics of the Sample

The structured questionnaires were administered to a total number of 80 respondents in Bangalore. The responses given by the 80 respondents were productive and useful for our research. A most of the sample respondents (58.1 percent) are male respondents and remaining (41.9 percent) are female. A majority of the respondents (67.8 percent) is in the range of 25-40 years of age, and (32.2 percent) fall in the age group of below 25 years. While (64.1 percent) are married, (35.9 percent) are single.

The most of the sample respondents (28.8 percent) are employed in either private and government organizations, (15.1 percent) are students, (13.7 percent) are business men, (12.4 percent) are self-employed, (11.4 percent) are house wives, (11.3 percent) are professionals and remaining (7.4 percent) are retired persons.

While a majority of the sample respondents (62.9 percent) have computer literacy and the experience of surfing the internet, (37.1 percent) don't have computer literacy. The most of the sample respondents (64.0 percent) are not able to access the internet at home or at the workplace and (36.0 percent) are able to access the internet at home or at the office. More than half of the sample respondents (61.6 percent) are holding smart phones and remaining (38.4 percent) don't have the smart phones.

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics such as Mean (μ) and Standard Deviation (σ) were computed to determine the nature of the research variables in response to users' perceived value on the digital banking services offered by commercial banks in Bangalore. The Table1 indicates a set of seven research constructs concerning the users' perceived views on digital banking services. When the respondents were requested to rate their level of agreement with a set of statements using a 5-point Like scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), the consequent responses obtained in this regard were presented in Table1 along with the results of One-Way ANOVA and reliability test.

According to Table1, the results were found to be very different from the mid-value 3.0 Of these seven constructs, "Convenience" was observed to be the significant construct with the highest mean score of 3.94 with respect to the users' perceived value on the digital banking services rendered by commercial banks in Bangalore. Followed by, the other significant constructs identified with the help of factor analysis in this study were "Ease of Use" with the mean score of 3.87, "Time Saving" with the mean score of 3.82, "Cost Effective" with the mean score of 3.44, "Government Supports" with the mean score of 3.26, and "Trust & Reliability" with the mean score of 3.14. On the other hand, the construct "Privacy & Security" was viewed to be insignificant with the lowest mean score of 2.24 in response to the users' perceived value on the quality of digital banking services provided by commercial banks in Bangalore.

The significant constructs of digital banking services were also identified using the one-way ANOVA as shown in Table1. Results of one-way ANOVA reveal that the 'Ease of Use', 'Convenience', 'Trust & Reliability', 'Cost Effective', 'Time Savings', and 'Government Support' were the pertinent factors that significantly influence the quality of digital banking services at $p < 0.05$. Meanwhile, privacy & security of digital banking was found to be highly insignificant with regard to the service quality of digital banking services provided by commercial banks in Bangalore.

A reliability analysis was carried out to check for the seven critical success dimensions of digital banking services generated through factor analysis. A rule of thumb suggests that the acceptance Cronbach alpha value should exceed 0.7 (Hair et al., 1998). Table 2 depicts a summary of the beta scores of all the response rankings of the dimensions that affect the quality of digital banking services in Bangalore. All dimensions exhibit a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of at least 0.71, indicating that the questionnaire (n=272) has attained rather high level of reliability for the various parameters of digital banking or virtual banking in general. Hence, all variables are retained. Among these dimensions, the dimension of 'Security & Privacy' has the lowest ranking of Cronbach alpha of 0.812, followed by the 'Trust & Reliability' with 0.864. The dimension of 'Convenience' has the highest ranking of Cronbach alpha with 0.988.

Table - 1 ANOVA and reliability test on salient dimensions of digital banking services

S. No.	Dimensions	Mean Score	SD	F-value	p-value	Sig.	Cronbach's α
1	Ease of Use	3.87	0.042	32.04	0.031*	Sig.	0.972
2	Convenience	3.94	0.121	35.11	0.021*	Sig.	0.988
3	Trust & Reliability	3.14	0.342	22.46	0.046*	Sig.	0.864
4	Cost Effective	3.44	0.742	28.75	0.036*	Sig.	0.937
5	Time Saving	3.82	0.984	33.45	0.028*	Sig.	0.968
6	Privacy & Security	2.24	0.062	17.27	0.068**	Not Sig.	0.812

One-Way ANOVA of Research Variables

The second hypothesis (H2) of this study was framed to test for a significant difference in the users' perceived view regarding various facets of digital banking services on the basis of their demographic characteristics. To examine if demographic variables influence the users' perceived view on various facets of digital banking services, the relationships between various demographic variables were tested with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results were presented in Table 5.

On the basis of frequencies and percentages of the demographic profile, meaningful light of conclusion can be derived. Results of the one-way ANOVA show that the different age group, education level, income level, computer literacy, internet accessibility at home/office of the sample respondents were found to have the significant relationships with the users' perceived value on various aspects of e-banking such as ease of use, convenience, trust & reliability, cost effective, time savings, and privacy & security.

Table 2 Relationship between demographic variables and users' perceived value on various aspects of e-banking services

S. No.	Demographic Variables	F-value	p-value	Sig.
1	Gender	6.233	0.425**	Not Sig.
2	Age	10.243	0.041*	Sig.
3	Marital Status	5.144	0.512**	Not Sig.
4	Education Level	11.341	0.038*	Sig.
5	Occupation	8.264	0.052**	Not Sig.
6	Computer Literacy	13.256	0.024*	Sig.
7	Internet Accessibility at Home/Office	12.253	0.030*	Sig.
8	Smart phone Availability	4.326	0.564**	Not Sig.

Note: *Denotes Significance at $p < 0.05$

**Denotes Insignificance at $p < 0.05$

Conclusion & Managerial Implications

As the paradigm of information technology rapidly changes the fabrics of banking sectors in today's modern world, the operation of e-banking has become more indispensable, paramount and diversified in the fierce competitive business environment. Specializing in unlimited, speedy and convenient services, digital banking has transformed the conventional system of banking in many developed and developing countries.

The statistical results of the one-way ANOVA show that the different age group, education level, computer literacy, internet accessibility at home/office of the sample respondents were found to have the significant relationships with the users' perceived value on various aspects of e-banking services such as ease of use, convenience, trust & reliability, cost effective, time savings, privacy & security, and Government supports.

The present study represents future implications for the digital bankers who can attract more customers electronically and online by adopting stringent measures on security & privacy of digital banking services. The outcome of this particular research was confined to the sample size and responses provided by the sample respondents. The future researchers are left with a wide spectrum to expand the boundary of the current research by taking a large and diverse sample including all areas of Bangalore. Based on the results of this study, the following managerial implications were drawn by the researchers:

- From the perspective of banking products and services being offered through electronic means and online, digital banking is nothing more than traditional banking services delivered through the backbone of electronic communication delivery channels. The e-delivery channels include direct dial-up connection, private network, public network, telephone, personal computer, ATM, Kiosk, mobile phone, and an easy access to Internet & WWW, digital banking is increasingly used by banks for receiving instructions and delivering their products and services to their customers effectively.
- The diversity in computer, communication and software technologies used by the banks vastly increases the challenges facing the online and digital bankers. In this chapter, an effort has been made to give an overview of the technologies commonly used in e-banking. An attempt has been made in order describe the concepts, techniques and technologies which are related to the privacy and security including the physical security. The banks which are planning to offer digital banking should have explicit policy on the security and privacy.

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